

MODERN JUDICIAL ADMINISTRATION IN BULGARIA - STATUS AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

The report presents the judicial administration in Bulgaria in terms of structure and activity. The aim of the report is to analyze the need for its modernization through the prism of digitalization of court proceedings. The paper focuses on the training of court officials at different educational levels and presents the experience in training bachelors at the University of Economics-Varna. As a result of the study, conclusions and generalizations are drawn with a practical orientation linking the modern judicial administration with quality education of judicial officers and continuous training and improvement of knowledge, skills and competence. The aim of the report is to briefly analyze the Bulgarian judicial administration in its current state and in the light of the trends and policies for its development, both through the prism of the theoretical analysis and in view of the practices of IU-Varna in the training of judicial officers. The study advocates the need for training of highly qualified judicial officers, in accordance with the dynamics of the needs of the judicial system and in order to have an effective justice system. The material uses traditional methods of scientific research, such as normative, comparative law, induction and deduction. As a result of the conducted research, some conclusions can be drawn that the modern training of competent and highly qualified civil servants implies a broad system of theoretical legal and managerial knowledge, good practical experience, building on and accompanying the course of training, a high level of digital competencies, as well as social, business and protocol communication skills. The present study was developed in the framework of the national scientific project NPI № 57 of 2022 on "Legal Relations and Status of Persons in the Judiciary in the Conditions of Digitalization".

Keywords: court administration, court employees, training, court administration structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technologies are part of all areas of life. In this respect, the justice system is also under the influence of digitalization, with the expectations of citizens and businesses, as well as of the European institutions, to digitalize the justice process and improve the quality of service delivery increasing daily. In view of this, the development of e-justice is an essential prerequisite for the successful implementation of the reform of the judiciary, which is one of the key issues for the democratic processes in Bulgaria and its compliance with European requirements. A step in the development of the process was

made in view of the constraints imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic, which confronted the judiciary with the need for a well-functioning remote justice system. The introduction, implementation and development of e-Justice requires qualified judicial officers committed to ensuring the operation of information and communication technologies in the judiciary.¹

The digitalization of processes in the judicial system is a process that has started, but its effectiveness is related to many factors, among which is the education of IT specialists with knowledge in the field, as well as the need for specialized computer training of judicial officers, a prerequisite for the effective performance of their duties in relation to the provision of electronic services and electronic access to justice. E-justice is also linked to the development of the digital economy. The European Parliament has made its recommendations for the development and establishment of a common regulatory framework through the new provisions of the Digital Services Act (Radev, E (2020).

In this context, the relevance of the topic for the judicial administration is undeniable, both from a scientific and practical point of view. Quality and efficient court administration is the absolute basis for effective and efficient justice and in this sense it implies a qualitatively different level of training of court officials, oriented directly to the needs of the justice delivery mechanism.

The aim of this paper is to briefly analyze the Bulgarian judicial administration in its current state and in the light of the trends and policies for its development, both through the prism of theoretical analysis and with regard to the practices of the IU-Varna in the training of judicial officers. On the basis of the analysis, conclusions are drawn to summarise the main challenges facing higher education and recommendations are made for improving the legal framework.

The study advocates the need for training of highly qualified judicial officers in accordance with the dynamics in the needs of the judiciary and in order to have an effective justice system.

The material uses traditional research methods such as normative, comparative law, induction and deduction. The report is compliant with national legislation as of October 2023.

2 HIGHER EDUCATION - FROM TRADITIONALISM TO E-TRANSFORMATION

The establishment of the first Bulgarian higher education institutions was after the liberation of the country, accordingly the legal framework in this period was characterized by the adoption of separate acts and the lack of a unified state policy. Nevertheless, Bulgarian higher education has its deep historical traditions (Tsanev, 1988) (Panayotov, 1999) (Popov, 2007) (Dimitrova, 2016). A number of scholarly publications have been devoted to the management of higher education institutions (Dimitrov, 2003) (Vutsova, 2015) (Dimitrova, 2020), the quality of higher education (Dimitrova, 2013)(Dimitrova, 2022)(Dimitrova, 2022a), higher education policy (Pilev, 2003), the economic prospects for higher education (Dimitrov G. et. al, 2001) (Dimitrov G., on European perspectives of Bulgarian higher education institutions, 2005), (Berberova-Vulcheva, 2010). For the purposes of this paper, the evolution of Bulgarian higher education will not be traced in detail, but only the main stages through which it is passing will be outlined. The aim of this retrospective is to illustrate the relationship of the different historical periods with the development of social relations in the country and their interdependence, which also reflects on the normative base in force for the respective period, respectively affecting the teaching methods in higher education. At each stage, universities should ensure the quality of the educational process so that graduating students are prepared to adequately participate in the labour market and to be successfully realised. In this regard, an important part of these relations are employment relations, the legal framework of which is also undergoing dynamic development (Banov, 2020a). As this legal framework is characterized by its general applicability also in relation to the academic staff involved in the implementation of higher education in Bulgaria, it invariably has a certain impact on its overall development (Banov, 2018) (Banov, 2020b).

The first period corresponds to the capitalist development of Bulgaria and has a time frame starting after the Liberation and lasting until 1944. This stage is characterized by the emergence of the first higher education institutions and the establishment of the foundations in the normative framework of higher education and the creation of the first Bulgarian universities.

The second period coincides with the socialist development of Bulgaria and can be limited to the period 1944-1989. At this stage, the national legal system had already been extinguished and, accordingly, there

¹ Welcome speech by Miglena Tacheva at the opening of the round table "The e-justice challenge for the judiciary", 26.11.2021 Sofia

was a normative framework corresponding to state policy.

The third stage is after the democratic changes of 1989, when, building on the normative framework established in the previous period and on the already established traditions in education, a process of modernization of higher education began.

At the present moment we can talk about a radically different evolutionary stage in the development of higher education in Bulgaria within the third stage. We associate it with internationalization as a process, as well as with digitalization in social relations, the change in the economy based on electronic transformation and the entry of artificial intelligence, both in labour relations and in the field of education.

Therefore, it is not without reason that we can talk about innovative higher education in Bulgaria, which strives to keep pace with the technological revolution, but also to embody in educational models the traditions, achievements and specificities of autonomous Bulgarian higher education institutions.

The term innovation is of Latin origin (in "in" and novus "new"). It was first introduced in the early 20th century, being used by Joseph Stumpeter in 1912. A significant contribution in clarifying the concept of innovation was made by P. Drucker, who considered it as an economic phenomenon projected in management, marketing, advertising, entrepreneurship (Drucker 1992, p.18). According to the author, "systemic innovation consists in the purposeful and organized search for change and in the systematic analysis of the opportunities it can offer for economic and social innovation (ibid:23). Innovation in education also has its development, which encompasses different patterns both corresponding to the educational level and from the educational policy in the specific country.

In considering the issues of innovation, we cannot ignore the impact it has on the actors involved. For this reason, the issue cannot be discussed in isolation, but should be placed alongside another concept of new importance in the field of education. It is no coincidence that the consideration of the term "trust ecosystem" has come into use, and in the field of higher education it can be seen in several aspects.

The ecosystem can be classified into different types, in terms of the entities it comprises, respectively the processes it covers. According to this criterion we distinguish:

- First of all, an ecosystem comprising the traditional subjects of higher education institutions, i.e. academic and administrative staff and trainees (students, PhD students and postgraduate students). In this case, we are talking about an internal university ecosystem (or ecosystem in a narrow sense), where the construction of "trust" should be studied with a view to the digitalization of processes. These can be processes related to teaching, to administrative services in a digital environment, as well as to the conduct of research by members of the academic staff, as well as involving trainees in the research process in order to develop their research potential (Serafimova, D. (2021). In Bulgaria, the basis of this ecosystem is laid down in national legislation, but its specificity and development is regulated in internal university acts, adopted in accordance with state policy but reflecting the progress of the particular university.
- Secondly, the interaction between higher education institutions and their integration into alliances involving both national and foreign universities should be considered. This ecosystem is of the "open type" and aims at both sharing resources and pooling efforts in order to reach a high level of competitiveness of the educational service in the context of e-transformation. In this type of ecosystem, the sources are both national for Bulgaria and foreign and international with a view to participating in international alliances and subordinating norms beyond national boundaries.
- Third, stands the ecosystem with the largest and most diverse composition of participating entities. Here we can include both the interaction between HEIs and state institutions (ministries, agencies, etc., conducting state policy) and between HEIs and business. This ecosystem is of the most open type, accordingly the challenges within it are related to the different pace of penetration of digitalization and artificial intelligence.

All these issues concerning the ecosystem of trust in the sphere of higher education have been studied only in a fragmentary way in theory, and legislatively they are not yet subject to regulation in the Bulgarian legal system. Both at the doctrinal and legislative level, the components of the ecosystem and the impact of innovations in higher education on the balance in these ecosystems are yet to be examined and regulated.

In order to provide relevant ideas and suggestions, this paper will present the applicable national sources governing higher education in Bulgaria, as well as outline the main challenges related to the legal framework.

First of all, at the national level the regulation is built on several hierarchical levels: the Constitution, Laws

(Law on Higher Education, Law on Development of Academic Staff in the Republic of Bulgaria), by-laws, acts of higher education institutions.

The dynamics in the social processes brought about by the fourth industrial revolution has also necessitated changes in the regulation of higher education, but at present the Bulgarian legislation in this sphere is subject to separate amendments and lacks a complete process of normative change that would cover all aspects as well as to foresee and regulate forthcoming changes in social relations and interrelations. As part of the priority areas for the development of higher education set out in the Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria for the period 2021-2030 are.

Secondly, there are the issues of the professions of the future, which should be foreseen, researched and universities should be ready to adapt their educational programmes, respectively teaching documentation, to offer training in them. (Serafimova, D., Andreeva, A. (2021)

Third, but not least, are the issues concerning the interaction between universities and business. This relationship should be regulated both at the normative level and developed on the basis of subsequent acts and actions aimed at the implementation of norms in the real process of education and research. Changes to the Law on Education and Research in 2018 enabled up to 10 per cent of the total number of hours of the curriculum for the Bachelor's degree and up to 20 per cent of the total number of hours of the curriculum for the Master's degree to be conducted by outstanding specialists from practice (Kuyumdzhev, I., Andreeva, A., Dimitrova, D., (2022)). With the changes in the Law on Education, employers were provided with the opportunity to conclude contracts with students for internships during their studies and for securing a workplace after graduation. The costs of the training of these students will be fully or partially provided by the state budget, with reimbursement in the event of contract default (The Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria for the Period 2021-2030 was adopted by the 44th National Assembly on 17 December 2020).

In the field of education, innovations are perceived as patterns that transform the nature of learning, concerning the goal orientation, the structure of interactions between subjects, and their positions in the course of the learning process (Klarin 1995, pp. 47-48). According to the author, "innovation is not any novelty, but only those changes which are essential and are accompanied by changes in the overall image of the activity described as necessary and in the style of pedagogical thinking (ibid.). Digital technologies can be described as a combination of information, computing, communication and connectivity technologies (Bharadwaj, Sawy,Pavlou, Venkatraman, 2014), which enables the development of new products,business models, services and organizational forms (Fichman, Dos Santos, Zheng 2014).

For the sake of concreteness, the study will present some good practices of UE-Varna, as well as an opinion survey among students studying at the Master's degree level at the university. By Order No. RD09-328 / 09.02.2023 of the Minister of Education and Science the Development Policy of the University of Economics-Varna for the period 2023-2027 was approved.

The policy contains 6 objectives, 14 targets and 33 performance indicators with corresponding target values. Some new points in the Policy are: the development of the Varna Deep Technology Innovation Port (VDTIP) with the aim of making Varna a centre of attraction for the creation and implementation of deep technology innovations; Enhancing the effectiveness of practical training by increasing the relative share of disciplines involving practitioners; Providing support for student start-ups and supporting the application of the entrepreneurial approach to student learning by developing the UEVA Business Accelerator, etc.

3 TRAINING OF EMPLOYEES IN THE JUDICIAL ADMINISTRATION - PRACTICES OF UE-VARNA

UE - Varna is the first Bulgarian university in which the specialty of Judicial Administration has been opened in order to train personnel with the Bachelor's degree, as a consequence of a joint initiative of the Department of Legal Studies and the National Institute of Justice, dictated by the need on the one hand for quality trained judicial officers with the appropriate level of education and legal and managerial knowledge, and on the other - with adapted in view of the dynamics of social conditions and social environment complex legal and administrative - organizational training. Both the validation and the implementation of the curricula and programmes are based on several main guidelines, namely - complex and interdisciplinary theoretical training, extensive and active forms of practical trainings, events and joint initiatives with different levels of the judiciary, building a permanently established system of social and communicative skills and competences for adaptability and successful implementation of professional - theoretical and practical training.

Taking these guidelines into account, two lasting parallel components in the training process - theoretical and practical.

At the level of the theoretical basis, a wide range of fundamental theoretical knowledge in various areas of legal, administrative and managerial training is developed and applied through the established curricula and programmes, forming a system of basic and advanced concepts and institutes. In a systematic aspect, they overlap several main elements uniting the study of fundamental, special or elective subjects, namely:

- Foundation of a wide range of legal knowledge in the field of public and private law and procedure, through the study of fundamental, special or elective legal disciplines - Civil Law and Procedure, Administrative Law and Procedure, Criminal Law and Procedure, Labour and Social Security Law, Family and Succession Law, Property Law, Commercial Law and others.
- Managerial and administrative knowledge and competences studied in the aspects of their basic concepts, principles and trends of development or considering specific aspects necessary in view of the direct activity of the successful professional - in particular these are the disciplines of Human Resource Management in the Public Sector, Organization of Judicial Administration, Business Administration and Legal Stylistics, Administrative Culture and Ethics, Quality Management Systems in Public Administration and others.
- Contemporary and relevant to the dynamics of the judicial system and the management sector knowledge and competences related to the processes of digitalization of public relations or alternative means of dispute resolution - Legal Information Systems, Digital Communications, Access and Protection of Information, Electronic Justice, Mediation and out-of-court disputes, etc.
- Business and protocol communication skills, as well as conflict resolution and dispute resolution - through the disciplines related to administrative culture and administrative ethics, as well as studying the essence and nature of mediation procedures.

At the level of practice-oriented learning, the practice of the teaching department, guided by the vision of the inextricable and necessary link between theoretical learning and practical skills, applies two main policies:

- Accompanying and continuing through the various stages of training and according to its respective needs a wide system of practical events, including - meetings - discussions with practitioners and magistrates, public lectures, scientific - practical discussion forums, visits to various law enforcement institutions. The latter is realized through the wide network of established practices of cooperation, on the one hand, with the different levels of the judiciary - district, district, administrative and appellate courts - Varna, with the Supreme Administrative Court, Varna prison, and also with a number of bodies and institutions - Ombudsman of the Republic of Bulgaria, Institute of State and Law at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Commission for Protection against Discrimination, Institute of Mediation "Itera"- Varna and others. Successfully implemented over the years are the projects "Youth and Justice" - jointly with the District Court - Varna, "Civil Monitoring" - jointly with the Court of Appeal - Varna, "Law in Action" - jointly with the District Court - Varna, "Administrative Justice - Training in Practice" - jointly with the Administrative Court - Varna.
- Compulsory practical training, set as a stage of the special training with fully practical orientation and conducted in a real environment with a total of 240 hours.

All components of the overall policy and vision for the development of the specialty are subordinated to the idea of a sound scientific training, sustainable development of social, digital skills and competences and a building-up but accompanying practical - oriented training in order to maximize adaptability and application of theoretical knowledge. At the same time, permanently applied tendencies in training are also continuous updating of the training content so that it is maximally adapted to legislative and social changes, expanding the range of digital knowledge and skills at each level of training - theoretical or practical, synchronization of the requirements for knowledge acquisition in accordance with national and pan-European policies and strategies. In this sense, it fully corresponds and is in line with the knowledge, skills and competences provided for in the National Qualifications Framework of the Republic of Bulgaria and established in the light of the European Qualifications Framework (Baccalaureate Sub-Level 6b), namely - possession of extended and in-depth theoretical and factual knowledge in the field, including those related to the latest developments in the field, interpretation of the acquired knowledge by linking it with the application of facts and by critically perceiving, understanding and expressing theories and principles, the ability to manage administratively, under the influence of various interacting and difficult to predict factors, creativity and initiative in management activities, collecting, classifying, evaluating and interpreting data from the field in order to solve

specific problems, as well as applying the acquired knowledge and skills in new or unfamiliar conditions, logical thinking and broad personal outlook, etc.²

In conclusion, it can be summarized that the practice of training in the specialty of Judicial Administration provides grounds for several more characteristic conclusions, namely:

1. necessarily creating a lasting theoretical foundation of properly understood, applied legal concepts and institutes, as well as a good knowledge of the substantive and procedural legal framework,
2. the establishment of good management and administrative skills, as well as the ability to overcome conflicts and resolve disputes in a timely manner
3. Establishing knowledge of correct business and protocol communication
4. building a high level of academic and scientific language
5. Continuous practice-oriented training at every stage of the learning process
6. Encouragement of independent research and academic inquiry by the trainees, as is the practice of both the University and the Department through the organization and conduct of University Student Research Conferences and Student Research Conferences organized by the Department of Legal Studies. This, on the one hand, not only provokes and builds on the interest in legal and management sciences, but also encourages creative and scientific thinking, as well as activates a continuous upgrading and expansion of the acquired knowledge.

4 CONCLUSION

As a result of the study, some conclusions can be drawn and recommendations can be made.

The modern training of competent and highly qualified civil servants presupposes a broad system of theoretical legal and managerial knowledge, good practical experience, building on and accompanying the course of training, a high level of digital competencies, as well as social, business and protocol communication skills. This can be achieved through consistent training at different levels - secondary education, higher education at the "Bachelor" and "Master" levels, as well as through specialized training for the personnel of the judicial administration, taking into account their.

A modern and modern judicial administration is undoubtedly not so much a concrete vision as a continuous process of development and upgrading. The different and dynamic demands of the digital age, on the one hand, and the ever-increasing, new expectations of the judicial officer, on the other, imply the development of a system of competences, theoretical, practical and social skills that will enable successful professional realisation in favour of a better functioning judicial system.

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² National Qualifications Framework - https://www.navet.government.bg/bg/media/NQF_bg.pdf

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